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Deliverable Abstract

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project started in June 2022 and will deliver nine new EOSC-Core components in support of a FAIR research life cycle, bridging the gaps identified in the EOSC SRIA. More specifically, the components will enable an EOSC PID infrastructure, an EOSC research software infrastructure, support for sharing and access to metadata schemas and crosswalks and offer advanced research-intent driven discovery services over all EOSC repositories. This deliverable summarises the cross-integration beta technical status of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components and the use cases. The report is based on the input received by WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 via the milestones at M18 until M22.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
CAT	Compliance Assessment Toolkit, a service being developed in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project to assist with EOSC PID Policy compliance assessment
Compliance Assessment	The process of determining to what extent a service, object, organisation, or capabilities comply with a set of criteria, based on reproducible tests.
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud
EOSC PID Policy	The policy being developed by the EOSC PID Policy Task Force to ensure a minimum standard of performance for the PID ecosystem in EOSC
FAIR	Principles based on community expectations in respect of research outputs - findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
FAIR-IMPACT	A EU-funded project that has as its main objectives to identify practices, policies, tools and technical specifications to guide researchers, repository managers, research performing organisations, policy makers and citizen scientists towards a FAIR data management cycle. The focus will be on persistent identifiers (PIDs), metadata, ontologies, metrics, certification and interoperability.
FAIRCORE4EOSC	The FAIRCORE4EOSC project focuses on the development and realisation of core components for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation: Regulations aimed at protecting the right to privacy of individuals in the EU in a digital context.
Landscape Assessment	A milestone report produced by FOARCCORE4EOSC WP2 to assess the scope of case studies that may influence a conceptual model for compliance assessment.
PID	Persistent identifier: generally expected to be unique, resolvable, and persistent, but other features and performance aspects may apply.
RDA	The Research Data Alliance, an international organisation developing standards, recommendations, and best practices in respect of research data management using voluntary contributions.
TRUST	The principles that describe the community expectations in respect of trustworthy repositories.

CLARIN DOG	Digital Object Gateway.
CLARIN VCR	Virtual Collection Registry.

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Executive Summary

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), one of the pillars for the realisation of the European Strategy for Data, is an ecosystem of research data and related services that will enable and enhance seamless access to and reliable re-use of FAIR research outputs (including data, publications, software, etc.). One of the priorities highlighted in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) is the establishment of the Web of FAIR data and a Minimum Viable EOSC by 2027, featuring the core components and functions to enable EOSC to operate. The development of the EOSC-Core was initiated in the Horizon 2020 calls which have delivered a rich palette of use cases, demonstrations, data, services and tools. However, there are still challenges that require to be addressed.

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project started in June 2022 and will deliver nine new EOSC-Core components in support of a FAIR research life cycle, bridging the gaps identified in the EOSC SRIA. More specifically, the components will enable an EOSC PID infrastructure, an EOSC research software infrastructure, support for sharing and access to metadata schemas and crosswalks and offer advanced research-intent driven discovery services over all EOSC repositories.

This deliverable summarises the technical status of the cross-integration FAIRCORE4EOSC components BETA release. It is based on the Milestones D22 delivered by WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 the cross-integration BETA release. It also describes the cross-integration activities among the different components that initiated the support of the first BETA release of the case studies. It also presents the current status of the attempts and the plan to integrate the components developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC with existing EOSC Core Components.

1 Introduction

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), one of the pillars for the realisation of the European Strategy for Data, is an ecosystem of research data and related services that will enable and enhance seamless access to and reliable re- use of FAIR research outputs (including data, publications, software, etc.). One of the priorities highlighted in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) is the establishment of the Web of FAIR data and a Minimum Viable EOSC by 2027, featuring the core components and functions to enable EOSC to operate. The development of the EOSC-Core was initiated in the Horizon 2020 calls which have delivered a rich palette of use cases, demonstrations, data, services and tools. However, there are still challenges that require to be addressed. The FAIRCORE4EOSC project started in June 2022 and will deliver nine new EOSC-Core components in support of a FAIR research life cycle, bridging the gaps identified in the EOSC SRIA. More specifically, the components will enable an EOSC PID infrastructure, an EOSC research software infrastructure, support for sharing and access to metadata schemas and crosswalks and offer advanced research-intent driven discovery services over all EOSC repositories.

After the beta release described in deliverable D1.3¹. The implementation work continued with both the cross-integration of FAIRCORE4EOSC components and their integration with existing EOSC Core components. This deliverable is a report summarising the current status of the technical developments for the cross-integration FAIRCORE4EOSC components BETA release. It is based on the Milestones D22 delivered by WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 the cross-integration BETA release.

1.1 FAIRCORE4EOSC implementation Methodology

As explained in the Deliverable 1.3², the development of the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components revolves around four main implementation phases as depicted in the following Figure. All components to be developed will share this joint development timeline.

Phase 1: Collection of requirements and technical specifications

Phase 2: BETA release

Phase 3: Cross-integration BETA release

Phase 4: Production release and final documentation

Figure 1 – FAIRCORE4EOSC implementation Methodology

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/10518813>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/10518813>

At the time of the submission deadline of this deliverable (M22) the project is at phase 3, the **Cross-integration BETA release**.

1.2 Cross Integration BETA release

Following the Beta release of the MVP of each component, they were adopted by the use cases as required and the Cross Integration BETA Release signals the completion of their 1st pilot Integration. The cross integrations are pursued because they align with the use cases and requirements brought by the demonstrators. They actually serve as the driving force behind the integration efforts, as they represent the real-world scenarios and needs that the components aim to address.

Similarly in order to ease access to the newly developed components they were or planned to be integrated with a number of existing EOSC Core components such as AAI.

Figure 2 – Cross integration Diagram

The figure 2 above shows the cross integrations planned as they were recorded as requirements in Jira tickets and the table below show the number of requirements recorded per Use case for each FAIRCORE4EOSC Component.

Components	Components															T:
	CAT	CLIMATE	DEMO	DTR	MATH	MSCR	NATIONAL-SERVICE	PIDGraph	PIDMR	RAID	RDGraph	RSAC	SERVICES-AND-RDM	SSH	No component	
CAT	56	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	56
CLIMATE	0	44	0	13	0	12	0	9	0	10	8	0	0	0	0	44
DEMO	0	0	66	18	0	37	0	9	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	66
DTR	0	13	18	49	2	13	0	3	0	1	0	4	5	0	0	49
MATH	0	0	0	2	16	2	0	6	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	16
MSCR	0	12	37	13	2	73	11	1	0	0	0	4	6	0	0	73
NATIONAL-SERVICE	0	0	0	0	0	11	24	3	0	7	1	2	0	0	0	24
PIDGraph	0	9	9	3	6	1	3	46	0	2	7	0	0	3	0	46
PIDMR	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	70	0	0	0	0	5	0	70
RAID	0	10	0	1	2	0	7	2	0	204	4	0	1	0	0	204
RDGraph	0	8	15	0	0	0	1	7	0	4	56	0	0	1	0	56
RSAC	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	35
SERVICES-AND-RDM	0	0	0	4	0	4	0	0	0	1	0	0	10	0	0	10
SSH	0	0	0	5	0	6	0	3	5	0	1	0	0	19	0	19
No component	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	8
Total Unique Issues:	56	44	66	49	16	73	24	46	70	204	56	35	10	19	8	572

Figure 3 – Cross integration requirements matrix.

2 Case Studies Integrations

FAIRCORE4EOSC project follows a user-centric approach to the development of its components by leveraging use cases to guide the development process. Five user-centric case studies were identified to drive the development and testing of the new components ensuring they are tailored to the user needs (co-design). The Case studies in the FAIRCORE4EOSC projects are the following

- Case Study 1: Social Sciences & Humanities
- Case Study 2: Climate Change
- Case Study 3: Mathematics
- Case Study 4: European Integration of National-level Services
- Case Study 5: EOSC Service Providers RDM Communities

At the same time FAIRCORE4EOSC components are designed with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles throughout the research life cycle as one of the main goals. The user stories, best practices and requirements drawn by the case studies will be used to foster uptake of the new components beyond the project partners. Overall, by closely involving users through use cases and emphasising co-design principles, FAIRCORE4EOSC is aiming to develop components that are not only technically robust but also highly relevant and usable within the research community. They act as the initial users of the components, testing out the new functionalities and providing valuable feedback on their usability and maturity. They provide practical contexts for testing the functionalities of the components and help validate their effectiveness in real-world scenarios. They help identify areas for improvement and contribute to stabilising the functionalities of the components over time. This agile testing process allows for refinement and improvement of the components before broader deployment.

Over the past few months, Components and Case studies teams have collaborated closely to achieve cross-integrations. Through evaluation and integration efforts on the beta release of components, the testing of each component by at least one case study is ensured. This process has emphasised the significance of component maturity in facilitating successful integrations.

This figure 4 depicts the Case Studies cross-integration with FAIRCORE components. The colours in the lines represent each Case Study. Dotted line means that the integration will follow. Full line that the integration is tested.

Figure 4 – Case Studies cross-integration with FAIRCORE components.

The table 1 shows the number of Case Study Integrations per component, realised as of M22 and planned for the end of the project (M34):

Table 1 – Number of Case Study Integrations per component, realised as of M22 and planned for M34

Components	Number of case study integrations (M22)	Number of planned case study integrations (M34)
RD Graph	1	5
PID Graph	2	5
MSCR	3	5
DTR	4	5
PIDMR	2	2
RAiD	3	3
RSAC	1	2
SWHM	0	1

In the "case study vs component integration" matrix, shown in MS37 "Enabling Case-Studies on Beta Service releases" and included below, the same numbers are shown, but we have now split them out over each case study.

Table 2 – Case study vs component integration matrix

Case study vs component integration Timeline						
Components	Climate Change	EOSC Service Providers RDM Communities	European Integration of National-Level Services	Mathematics	Social Sciences & Humanities	
RD Graph	M34	M34	M34	M22	M34	
PID Graph	M34	M34	M22	M22	M34	
MSCR	M34	M22	M22	M34	M22	
DTR	M22	M22	M34	M22	M22	
PIDMR				M22	M22	
RAiD	M22	M22	M22			
RSAC			M34	M22		
SWH(M)			M34			

As shown in these tables all component beta releases have been tested by at least one case study (M22). In M22 most components have a decent integration coverage with the exception of the RD Graph, PID Graph and SWHM components. Most case studies have chosen to focus on the integration of the MSCR, DTR and PIDMR components earlier since these components required the most testing due to either the low maturity of the component or the fact that multiple of these components are required together to implement the defined user stories.

In the following paragraphs you will find information on the cross-integration of each Case Study with the components. Each Case study will be analysed in terms of how it interacts with the components developed as part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. This may involve outlining the specific functionalities of the components that are utilised or tested within each case study scenario. Details on how these functionalities contribute to achieving the goals of the case study and how these supports the FAIR research lifecycle are also described. The impact of the integrated components on the outcomes of each case study is also highlighted in the following paragraphs.

Overall, you will find a comprehensive overview of how the components developed within FAIRCORE4EOSC are applied within real-world research contexts like the supported Use Cases, showcasing their effectiveness in supporting FAIR principles and advancing the goals of the project.

2.1 Case Study 1: Social Sciences & Humanities

2.1.1 Introduction

The Social Sciences & Humanities case study is facing challenges to make services available and interoperable across different domains to ultimately achieve "horizontal" services across sciences. CLARIN will integrate its Digital Object Gateway (DOG), the CLARIN Virtual Collection Registry and the Language Resource Switchboard with the EOSC MSCR, the EOSC DTR and the EOSC PIDMR in order to (i) make their functions and content available beyond the SSH Cluster borders to all EOSC users, (ii) benefit from the services and content (e.g. data types, crosswalks) available from other communities and infrastructures via the EOSC MSCR and DTR. Moreover, the integration with EOSC registries will make CLARIN domain language data resources available via the EOSC PIDGraph and the EOSC RDGraph.

The adopted components are **DTR, MSCR, PIDGraph, PIDMR, RDGraph**.

2.1.2 Cross-integrations achieved

Both the DTR and PIDMR have been tested with the Digital Object Gateway. DTR is onboarded by supporting querying and exposing DTR types for use in the Virtual Collection Registry and Switchboard. At the same time the functionalities of PIDMR have been tested and the resolution of PIDs other than Handles and DOIs will allow CLARIN to extend the range of external identifier systems CLARIN services can support.

In addition, work has been done to define and register a DTR type to support complex data types. The Virtual Collection Registry has been tested with the MSCR. This has resulted in the registration of a couple of schemas (one CMDI profile and TEI variant) into the MSCR. For these schemas we have created a crosswalk. On the VCR side, functionality has been implemented to query for schemas and crosswalks and finally download a crosswalk to run the transformation on the Virtual Collection Registry side and use the result to enhance the user experience when adding references, potentially from other domains.

This is shown in a schematic way in the following figure, see Figure 5. Components that have been included in the integration work for M22 have been highlighted in green.

Figure 5 – Case Study 1: Social Sciences & Humanities cross-integration with FAIRCORE4EOSC components

Usability of the MSCR UI was quite challenging. There are quite a bit of rough edges. With the help of the MSCR team we managed to register the schemas and crosswalks. Usability and discoverability of schemas and crosswalk is important if we want to support "horizontal" interoperability. Integration work to improve discoverability of our data in the PIDGraph and RDGraph has been scheduled for M34 as this requires more discussion first.

2.1.3 Cross-integrations next steps

The next steps are described below:

- Continue to improve the MSCR integration in the Virtual Collection Registry. The management and discoverability of schemas and crosswalks in the MSCR will be evaluated.
- Further integration of the Digital Object Gateway with the DTR, PIDMR, Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry.
- Evaluate and discuss the options to improve the PIDGraph and RDGraph integration.

2.1.4 Expected benefit

Currently we are only supporting handle and DOI resolution in our Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry services. The Digital Object Gateway integration with the PIDMR will extend our persistent identifier support with ark and urn:nbn, SWHids and any other identifier supported by the PIDMR in the future. This immediately lowers the barrier for cross domain use-cases by supporting resources identified by these new identifier systems to be used as input in the switchboard and to be referenced by identifier (as opposed to URL) in virtual collections.

Integration with the DTR into the Digital Object Gateway will also lower the barrier for automated workflows through the use of extended media types that allow us to store more information with the type, including links to broader types to create taxonomies, that is relevant in processing the underlying resource.

The MSCR integration offers us better strategies to extract relevant information from resources added to a virtual collection, including resources from other domains. This extra information is used to provide a better user experience when adding references to a collection. Currently the user is required to provide basic metadata for each reference. When adding a lot of references this can be a tedious process. With the MSCR integration we can convert the referenced object into a simple schema similar to Dublin Core and use this to extract the relevant information. This approach only works if the object added to a collection points to a metadata file or to a data object with a header which can be processed with an existing crosswalk. Over time we expect the number of crosswalks to increase, but creation and discoverability of these crosswalks is important.

2.2 Case Study 2: Climate Change

2.2.1 Introduction

The Climate case study aims to demonstrate how the ENES community (European Network for Earth System Modeling) can benefit from integrating DTR, RAiD, PIDGraph and/or RDGraph and MSCR as part of the data delivery workflow to generate and provide data provenance information alongside research data. Using the DTR, selected ENES data collections will receive identifiers to define the relationships between data collections and datasets, and between datasets and datafiles. Using RAiD, it should be possible to link climate datasets with corresponding projects and research activities to credit initiatives that enable the data generation process. RAiDs could provide (domain agnostic) users with an aggregated view of the whole context (data, software, people involved, etc.). All this information will be made available to B2FIND, the EUDAT discovery service, and thus discoverable via the interdisciplinary search portal. This metadata will also be made available to Open Science Gateways via interfaces and presented as RDGraph and PIDGraph. An area of intensive work is the improvement of information that enables meaningful crosswalks. The focus on improving the prerequisites for machine-aided analysis, including semantic aspects, is of high priority in this project due to the generally high data volumes and the high interdisciplinary requirements.

2.2.2 Cross-integrations achieved

RAiD and DTR have been successfully tested. PIDGraph and/or RDGraph will be exploited later, once the necessary RAiD and DTR information for the use case has been ingested. Currently, it seems that PIDGraph offers all the required features. Therefore, the initial focus will be on PIDGraph. An indirect integration with the RDGraph exists, since data from the PIDGraph is consumed into the RDGraph.

RAiDs can be created and updated for community projects and related objects. Work on detailed metadata requirements is ongoing. The potential to create RAiD graphs using related RAiDs through the PIDGraph is promising. However, verification is pending as RAiD and PIDGraph have to prepare the needed test environment.

DTR has been filled with community variable types as well as a community profile supporting a machine-aided interpretation of climate dataset collections.

A first test demo was successful, but it is unclear whether all DTR metadata has been filled in correctly and what improvements can be made.

The following figure explains how the three „main“ components work. The Handle PID benefits from the DTR providing a definition for the interpretation of collections, datasets and files and related DOIs. DOIs and related RAiDs – coming from the PIDGraph – extend and complete the data provenance.

Figure 6 – Case Study 2: Climate Change 4cross-integration with FAIRCORE4EOSC components

MSCR is currently under review. One area of intensive work is to improve the information that can enable meaningful crosswalks.

2.2.3 Cross-integrations next steps

The next steps are described below:

- Further optimise the use of RAiD and DTR and test the outcome of the PIDGraph.
- Re-evaluate and discuss the use case for the MSCR.

2.2.4 Expected Benefit

Using RAiD, it should be possible to link climate datasets with corresponding projects and research activities to credit initiatives that enable the dataset generation process. Additionally, this also depends on the functionality of the PIDGraph, which still needs to be verified. If RAiD and PIDGraph are functioning properly, a potential user of climate data will hopefully gain a comprehensive or at least an improved understanding of a given research topic due to the enhanced data provenance.

The DTR appears to be a useful tool for providing clear and concise definitions and descriptions of climate data and data collections. This could help group different data properties and attributes for the diverse needs of climate data. Automated validation and translation of these standardized metadata definitions is crucial for machine-actionable access to climate data.

The MSCR component facilitates the translation of climate vocabulary, allowing for cross-disciplinary understanding. The metadata should enable social scientists to understand climate scientists and vice versa, even when referring to different project variables.

2.3 Case Study 3: Mathematic

2.3.1 Introduction

The mathematical community represented by FIZ Karlsruhe - Leibniz Institut für Informationsinfrastruktur proposes the integration of zbMATH Open and swMATH services, as well as of the related manually curated

and aggregated metadata, with the FAIRCORE4EOSC components. This is achieved by integrating research software metadata and links in the EOSC RD- and PIDGraph and integrating with EOSC PIDMR. As a consequence, zbMATH Open and swMATH and related content will become available for discovery and stats via EOSC. Moreover, they will be able to enrich their metadata by interlinking to other objects (e.g. organisations, authors, datasets, services) via the PIDGraph and RDGraph and overall widen their visibility to other disciplines, users, services via the EOSC.

Currently a cross-integration with PID Metaresolver is in progress. PIDMR supports and resolves the zbl identifier for math articles. The PID Metaresolver solves the Zbl identifiers used for the zbMATH Open articles and the Software Hash Identifiers (SWHID) used to index the source code of mathematical software referenced in swMATH .

With the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, the Department of Mathematics of the FIZ Karlsruhe is pushing much effort toward making metadata accessible to the scientific community. FIZ Karlsruhe is currently processing zbMATH Open and swMATH metadata to expose them in a standardized and OAI-PMH server hosted by the MaRDI (Mathematical Research Data Initiative infrastructure). It is planned to integrate the MaRDI infrastructure more into the EOSC ecosystem, directly contributing to enriching the PIDGraph and the RDGraph, and specifically software metadata into Software Heritage through the RSAC-Math subcomponent.

2.3.2 Cross-integrations achieved

As a compliant OAI-PMH service endorsed by DataCite, the PIDGraph facilitates the enhanced interconnection of mathematical metadata with other scholarly entities. Initial mappings confirm potential rich interconnections between mathematical entities and beyond, leading to enriched entity linking within the domain-specific knowledge graph of mathematics. Furthermore, the RDGraph, a scientific knowledge graph supported by OpenAIRE, will be seamlessly enriched since fewer restrictions on DOIs exist since OpenAIRE indexes entities.

Figure 7 – Metadata of mathematical software and articles will be seamlessly integrated into the FAIRCORE4EOSC components.

We expect to improve the accessibility and discoverability of mathematical resources and inspire other institutions to adopt the FAIR components developed by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. Recently, the PIDMR component supports zbMATH identifiers for articles, helping to ensure the reliability and discoverability of persistent identifiers in Open Science. Last but not least, preliminary works have been achieved to partially expose the Mathematical Subject Classification (MSC) into the Data Type Registry (DTR) component, setting the MSC classification as a standard classification scheme for mathematics.

2.3.3 Cross-integrations next-steps

The next steps of the cross-integration are described below

- Set up a preliminary workflow to ingest metadata into both the PIDGraph and the RDGraph.
 - validate metadata formats with PIDGraph and RDGraph
 - ingest all the relevant metadata into the OAI server of the MaRDI infrastructure (ongoing work) of relevant vocabularies (e.x Datacite) with the XML file format.
- Investigate the integration with the MSCR to expose the software metadata into the Codemeta format based on a similar strategy used to expose our metadata to the DataCite vocabulary.
- Investigate the possibility of the PIDMR supporting the new software identifiers
- Investigate the possibility of exposing a more comprehensive range of the MSC into the DTR component

2.3.4 Expected Benefit

This work will advance the FAIRness compliance of mathematical entities supported by zbMATH Open. The RSAC component promises to help mathematicians find source code with long-term safe hyperlinks for software developed with standard forges like GitHub or GitLab and indexed with the SWHID, a reliable identifier for software source code. Metadata registries of swMATH, made available in CodeMeta format, can be deposited on Software Heritage to be preserved in the long run. Last, swMATH will support features to cite software, which should be helpful for conveniently citing software.

The two graph components supported by FAIRCORE4EOSC are promising core components to augment the mathematicians' user experience. A suitable functionality like Community request for the RDGraph, which already supports zbMATH Open authors examples, and the GraphQL for the PIDGraph, promises an exciting path to harvesting and extracting rich scientific graphs for mathematics. Identifying and comparing mathematics metadata exposed by other services could also be very insightful.

Aside from that, the PIDMR seamlessly supports article identifiers for mathematics, turning Zbl identifiers used by zbMATH Open and exposed in other services into verifiable indexes.

Last, The DTR supports a feature for ontologies named *taxonomyNode*, easing the process of exposing a scientific classification like the Mathematics Subject Classification (MSC). The *parentNode* feature is relevant to exposing tree classification, as the one exposed in the Mathematics Subject Classification. We are looking forward to exposing a wider part of the MSC in the DTR in the future.

2.4 Case Study 4: European Integration of National-level Services

2.4.1 Introduction

This case study showcases enrichment of both the national research graphs and the EOSC RDGraph by facilitating their interoperability using the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components. This case study will upgrade the CERIF (Common European Research Information Format) metadata schema, to enable the mapping of the OpenAIRE, the Finnish Research.fi, the Dutch Open Knowledge Base and the Greek Helix schemas to CERIF, by using the MSCR and possibly supplemented by the DTR. By utilising the MSCR cross-walk capability the exchange of information between the services can be facilitated. The resulting national research graphs can be used to highlight, for example, EOSC-related contributions or international collaborations within a particular national context. The new EOSC RAiD service enhances the capacity for creating durable links between research entities, by registering PIDs for research entities and bundling project related PIDs in the RAiD record, which is harvestable and ingested into the RDGraph.

The adopted components: **DTR, MSCR, PIDGraph, RAiD, RDGraph, RSAC**

The National-level Services case study involves piloting the integration of three national CRIS systems from Finland, the Netherlands and Greece in selected EOSC Core components. Within the CRIS domain, there are known challenges with interoperability of systems, manual conversions of metadata schemas and identifierless research objects. However, national built CRISs for research graph information could be an invaluable source for, for example, research assessment, or to highlight EOSC-related contributions if interoperability can be achieved.

2.4.2 Cross-integrations achieved

PIDGraph integration has been tested for enriching the research metadata on outputs, exploring workflows and implementing them in national CRIS-systems. At the end of the initial pilot phase, a first version for finding new relations for data objects from PIDGraph is now ready. Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) has been identified as a crucial component as the interoperability of research information is highly central in this case study and resolving issues with the interoperability of CRIS-like metadata is prioritized. During the pilot phase both CERIF2 and research.fi data models have been successfully registered to MSCR. DTR has been initially evaluated on how it can be employed (together with MSCR) to facilitate (a) better documentation of the standards, (b) operation of metadata transformations, e.g. from various institutional systems to the national Publinova, and from Publinova to e.g. OpenAIRE, or (c) easy migration from e.g. current formats (like DIDL/MODS) to the new CERIF format. The Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) has been tested with legacy project data. Both REST endpoint and manually adding information in the demo version were tested and creating a RAiD for a project has been successful for both.

The amount of data made querying PIDGraph challenging, and figuring out the appropriate filters took some time. The support of a big number of requests at once was a challenge. Limiting the query to smaller files was and is important.

ORCID, currently being obligatory for contributors in the RAiD metadata schema, is challenging for historic data, but also in the case of non-academic people without ORCID's, leading projects (e.g. in more applied sciences). Also issues around the governance systems, such as the roles of research performing organisations and national level services, in this case CSC and SURF, in minting and maintaining RAiDs need to be solved.

In evaluating the DTR the following questions arose: how to record specific naming conventions, and how to deal with minor variants of a person's record?

2.4.3 Cross-integrations next-steps

The next steps with respect to the integration work for this case study are:

- Implement the new relations found from PIDGraph to research.fi by the beginning of 2025.
- For the RDGraph, the case study still needs to figure out the added value of the component to national CRIS systems before moving forward with importing or exporting data.
- The case study partners aim to register their data models to MSCR, and test mapping them with the CERIF data model to enable aggregating this information to OpenAIRE.
- The CS plans to pilot RAiD with research performing organizations in the Netherlands and Finland. The piloting aims at building a data model for a "project" entity based on the RAiD data model, integrating this data model to organizations' own systems, and figuring out the optimal governance model.

2.4.4 Expected Benefit

By implementing RAiD, the CS will improve discovery and reporting of project-based research, by facilitating the registration and exchange of project information and its relations to researchers, institutes, funding an output. In addition, by using the MSCR, the CS will improve the exchange of research information between local, national and international CRIS systems, by enabling the mapping of CRIS data models to and from the CERIF data model (as the common interchange model for CRIS related information). The CS will improve the discovery and reporting of research, by enriching the research objects available in CRIS systems with links between those research objects as well as with new related information, such as abstracts through integration with the PIDGraph.

The solution developed by this case study is intended to serve as a template for integration of further national research information systems with the EOSC-core.

2.5 Case Study 5: EOSC Service Providers RDM Communities

2.5.1 Introduction

EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure provides a suite of interoperable data services for all research disciplines. This case study answers the general need of research communities for interoperable data services that facilitate discovery, access and reusability of research data. To meet these requirements, EUDAT services B2FIND and B2SHARE will be enhanced and improved through the integration of the MSCR, DTR, RD- and PID Graphs, RAiD and CAT components. For example, research communities will benefit from the MSCR and DTR by being able to perform and validate the mapping of their specific metadata schemas to the EUDAT Extended and EUDAT core metadata schemas by themselves, whereas the RD- and PID Graphs and RAiD will be used to enrich the information on the datasets deposited to the EUDAT services. CAT will be used to assess and improve EOSC compatibility of B2SHARE.

The adopted components: **CAT, DTR, MSCR, PIDGraph, RAiD, RDGraph**

The aim of the Service Providers and Research Data Management Communities Case Study is to streamline dataset related metadata schema management, and overall, make it easier for scientific communities to utilise their own metadata schemas with a 3rd party dataset repository, such as EUDAT B2SHARE. In addition to metadata schema management, we will also improve dataset metadata capabilities and visibility, by making it possible to use Research Activity Identifiers on EUDAT B2SHARE service.

2.5.2 Cross-integrations achieved

We have successfully tested metadata schema registration in the MSCR service, successfully described EUDAT Extended metadata schema in DTR service via UI and REST API and implemented possibility to input Research Activity Identifiers to dataset metadata on EUDAT B2SHARE training instance for the PIDgraph.

Due to a lack of documentation combined with the complexity of the use-case, there have been some issues in testing crosswalk related features in the MSCR. During testing of PIDGraph, we identified an imbalance between metadata in EUDAT B2SHARE and PIDGraph, where some of EUDAT B2SHARE metadata could not be found from PIDGraph. Due to the development schedule of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit, we have been unable to test CAT.

2.5.3 Cross-integrations next steps

The next steps with respect to the integration work for this case study are:

- to continue to test the crosswalk features of MSCR
- add the description of community metadata schema to DTR, implement RAiD support for EUDAT B2SHARE, if there is a demand for it from our current user communities.
- Plan to fix the identified shortcomings in current integration between PIDGraph and EUDAT and implement means to automatically identify and highlight any future discrepancy between EUDAT B2SHARE dataset metadata and PIDGraph dataset metadata.
- Evaluate how we can achieve our RDGraph related goal: to make sure that metadata stored in EUDAT B2SHARE is available in RDGraph.
- Test and evaluate CAT use in EUDAT B2SHARE service.

2.5.4 Expected Benefit

One of the main benefits is the management of the Streamlining dataset related metadata schema by using DTR and MSCR services. By utilizing MSCR and DTR it will be easier to integrate and manage existing and new B2SHARE community metadata extensions. This will lead to a wider userbase and more detailed community metadata extensions. In addition, the EUDAT B2SHARE dataset metadata capabilities and visibility using RAiD identifiers and PIDGraph and RDGraph services are improved. Users will be able to input RAiD identifiers related to the dataset. Users will be able to see the relationship of their datasets to research activities identified using RAiD. Improvements in providing metadata to PIDGraph and RDGraph increases accuracy and correctness of B2SHARE dataset related metadata available to those services.

Finally, by making use of the Compliance Assessment Toolkit, the level of EOSC compatibility for EUDAT B2SHARE service is increased.

2.6 Conclusion

Based on the summaries of the case studies integrations, we've identified specific challenges related to maturity, particularly concerning the MSCR service on the user interface side and RAiD's integration with PIDGraph. However, we are optimistic that both teams will address and improve these issues effectively. Despite some open questions the case studies indicate that all planned integrations are feasible by Milestone 34. This progress demonstrates our commitment to advancing the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and enhancing its capabilities in supporting FAIR principles across diverse research scenarios.

3 Cross Components Integrations

After completing the implementation work of the BETA release of the components, described in deliverable D1.3³ - based on initial specifications - the cross component integration has commenced. This chapter summarises the status of the FAIRCORE4EOSC cross-components integration. The work described is based also on a number of milestones achieved during the previous months and especially;

- **MS15** RDGraph and PIDGraph BETA cross-integration software report
- **MS33** BETA cross-integration software report
- **MS28** Meta Resolver cross-integration software report
- **MS21** Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry, Data Type Registry, RAiD BETA cross-integration software report
- **MS8** Operational Beta Release of Services and Compliance Assessment Toolkit available

In the table below you may see the cross-integration of FAIRCORE4EOSC components. On the vertical column are the different FAIRCORE4EOSC Components. These components are either investigating or have already implemented the cross-integration with the components defined in the horizontal row. MSCR is a core service that other core services are integrating with in order to use its functionalities. That is why it is not in the vertical column.

Table 3 – Cross-integration of FAIRCORE4EOSC components

	CAT	RD Graph	PID Graph	MSCR	DTR	PIDMR	RAiD	RSAC	SWH(M)
CAT				X		X			
RD Graph				X		X		X	X
PID Graph				X		X	X		
DTR				X					
PIDMR	X				X				
RAiD		X	X						
RSAC		X	X	X					X

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/10518813>

The figure 8 depicts the cross-integration of the components by explaining the functionalities used by each component. Each colour in figure 8 represents the integrations of a Core service to others.

Figure 8 – functionalities used by each cross components Integrations.

In the following paragraphs you may find information about the cross-integration described for each component and benefits for planned integrations described from the perspective of the respective component.

3.1 EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)

3.1.1 Introduction

EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit is investigating the integration with other FAIRCORE components. Currently it is investigating the cross integration with the PID metaresolver.

PID Metaresolver Integration:

The CAT component aims to integrate the PID metaresolver into its framework, leveraging its capabilities to achieve two objectives: (1) generating resolution monitoring events for persistent identifiers (PIDs), and (2) maintaining and sharing metadata about PID services and providers. The integration will encompass several key functionalities. CAT will maintain a comprehensive database, leveraging a graph database structure, to store information about PID Stacks, assessments, and associated metadata. This requires a registry, documenting PIDs providers, services and their interrelations. CAT will host a broader spectrum of players in the PID Ecosystem (PID providers, PID authorities, and services) compared to the PIDMR, but the PID providers listed within the PIDMR will be treated as the main source of information. CAT also intends to harness resolution events, originating from the PIDMR, within its own resolution and persistence monitoring service. This will improve tracking and analysis of the resolution processes (link rot and content drift), and increase the visibility of these processes.

MSCR Vocabulary Service Integration:

Apart from PIDMR, CAT will also integrate with the MSCR Vocabulary service. CAT will map a vocabulary or registry to the vocabulary service as an externally semantic service. The support for the listing and querying of available vocabularies, registries, and the properties of these will be integrated in the CAT.

3.1.2 Expected Benefits

The described integration of the PIDMR into the CAT framework will bring significant benefits to the assessment of EOSC PID Policy compliance for Persistent Identifiers. By leveraging the capabilities of the PIDMR and enhancing resolution monitoring, CAT strengthens its ability to assess compliance with the EOSC PID Policy and support the reliable and persistent identification of research outputs, contributing to FAIR in the process.

3.2 EOSC Research Discovery Graph Service (RDGraph)

3.2.1 Introduction

One of the main goals of the RDGraph was to pilot integration with a number of FAIRCORE4EOSC components. These integrations were documented in Milestone 15 - RDGraph and PIDGraph BETA cross-integration software report. The first step was to analyse the provided functionalities of the different FAIRCORE4EOSC components. Based on this investigation the team implemented or is planning the integration with the following components:

- EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC): This integration has already been done.
- PID Metaresolver: The integration is analysed and it is currently a work in progress
- Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR): The integration is analysed and it is currently a work in progress

EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC): RDGraph component integrates with the EOSC Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC) component through the OpenAIRE and Software Heritage connector. During the graph provisioning process, Software Hash identifiers are retrieved from Software Heritage (SWH) for all software entities within the graph. These identifiers are then made available via both the RDGraph portals (<https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu/>) and the associated graph APIs. Additionally, software code repositories existing in the RDGraph but not yet indexed in SWH are forwarded to the SWH APIs for saving and indexing purposes.

PID Metaresolver: As described in the M15 Report, this integration aims at streamlining the process of linking research products with projects, research communities or other research products and making this information available in the RDGraph. Users upload a file containing PIDs (e.g., DOIs) of the research products they wish to link, that may not currently be supported by the RDGraph. A mechanism is needed to fetch the required metadata from different providers. PID Metaresolver can play this role by facilitating the collection of metadata from different providers in a unified way. It acts as a centralised service for the RDGraph that can handle all the logic to resolve the PIDs to their corresponding metadata records.

Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR): RDGraph adopted the data model proposed by SKG-IF⁴ to enhance interoperability with other components. The SKG-IF provides a comprehensive framework for representing scholarly knowledge content, enabling the seamless exchange of information among diverse components regarding Scientific Knowledge Graphs. As described in M15 Report appropriate crosswalks from the SKG-IF data model to well established data models used in CRIS systems like CERIF⁵ will be created via the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR).

⁴ Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF: <https://skg-if.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>)

⁵ CERIF Common European Research Information Format

3.2.2 Expected Benefits

The described integrations as originally described in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project to advance the principles of FAIR in research data management. The integration with the **RSAC** component ensures the long-term preservation in the Software Heritage archive of research software in different disciplines, following the SIRS report and supporting quality metadata. The use of **MSCR** is used to enhance the interoperability and to facilitate data exchange with other components with the creation of crosswalks from the **SKG-IF** data model to well established data models. This interoperability is essential for fostering collaboration and maximising the utility of research data. Finally, the integration with **PID Metaresolver**, contributes to the support of new types of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) where the identification can be ensured while maintaining consistency and coherence in metadata usage across different contexts.

3.3 EOSC PID Graph Service (PIDGraph)

3.3.1 Introduction

In the PIDGraph Milestone 15 - RDGraph and PIDGraph BETA cross-integration software report the cross - integrations of PID Graph with other project components is described. The first step was to analyse the provided functionalities of the different FAIRCORE4EOSC components. Based on this investigation the team planned the integration with the following:

- **PID Metaresolver**: The integration is in the assessment stage
- **Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)**: The integration is analysed and it is currently a work in progress

PID Metaresolver: The PID Graph acknowledges the potential value in harnessing the PID Metaresolver (PIDMR) to enhance its capabilities. An essential aspect that demands attention is the PIDMR's capacity to address the scope of supported PIDs comprehensively. Notably, there is an identified potential for the PIDMR to play a pivotal role in resolving metadata for edge nodes and their related PIDs, thereby enriching the data dumps and offering a more comprehensive view of the interconnected elements within the PID Graph.

MSCR: The PID Graph is also investigating the adoption of the SKG-IF model for the component data file outputs. The first step is to look at to provision JSON data in the format proposed by the working group, and then at crosswalks from the DataCite JSON format to the SKG-IF model, utilising the MSCR component. Further to this, to facilitate increased interoperability and possibility of data exchange, we plan to work with the MSCR component to provide crosswalks from the PID Graph's native DataCite JSON and XML formats to other widely used schemas within the Scientific Knowledge domain, such as DC, JATS, Schema.org, and others.

3.3.2 Expected Benefits

PID Graph component currently is in the process of investigating the cross-integration with PID Metaresolver and MSCR component. Preliminary assessments indicate that the **PIDMR** could offer valuable functionalities such as resolving metadata for edge nodes in the PID Graph where metadata is currently lacking, removing the need for independent resolution and allowing end-users to access a richer graph output, albeit additional analysis is warranted to ascertain its utility beyond the current direct integrations within the PID Graph. This additional analysis will help determine the extent to which the PIDMR can enhance the functionality and capabilities of the PID Graph. Specific analysis of the edge nodes currently present and the utility of the **PIDMR** to resolve these metadata properties. The use of **MSCR** is following the RDGraph approach. Simultaneously, the integration involves leveraging crosswalks for native formats to enhance interoperability and facilitate data exchange with other components within the ecosystem.

3.4 EOSC PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR)

3.4.1 Introduction

This MS28 milestone is part of the work conducted in the context of Work Package 5 (WP5) EOSC PID Meta Resolver and PID Kernel Information Profiles. It summarises the cross integration of PID Metaresolver (PIDMR) with other FAIRCORE4EOSC components. The PIDMR brings notable advantages to researchers, organisations, and communities by fostering interoperability, and simplifying access to digital objects. The benefit of the service that stands out most, is that it offers a centralised access point for resolving various types of PIDs in a unified way. In this way, it relieves users from the necessity of navigating through the specifics of the different PID Provider services associated with different organisations or communities. Therefore, PIDMR plays a vital role in enhancing the discoverability and persistence of different research products and can be exploited by various FAIRCORE4EOSC components to facilitate different processes.

As already mentioned here are two different approaches of the cross-integration of the components. The first approach refers to the Integrations that benefit from PID Metaresolver capabilities. In this approach, components are integrated with the PID Metaresolver (PIDMR) to leverage its functionalities and benefits. The second approach refers to Integration for Utilising Functionalities of Other Components. The focus is on how PIDMR enhances or utilises the capabilities offered by other components, for example the use of DTR as described below, to enhance its own capabilities and improve the overall system's efficiency and effectiveness.

Integrations that benefit from PID Metaresolver capabilities:

The components that are going to use the functionalities of the PID Metaresolver are described below. The functionalities that are going to be used are described in the corresponding components paragraph.

- **Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph):** This is already described in the **RDGraph paragraph**.
- **PID Graph (PIDGraph):** This is already described in the **PIDGraph paragraph**.
- **Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT):** This integration is already described in the **CAT paragraph**.

Cross-Integration of Utilising Functionalities of Other Components

PID Metaresolver is going to integrate functionalities of the following components to approach interoperability.

Data Type Registry (DTR):

In the context of integrating PID Metaresolver within the Data Type Registry (DTR), the typing of PIDs will be standardised to ensure consistency across the backend infrastructure and API implementations. This approach allows for seamless integration and interoperability between different components of the system. A key aspect of this standardisation initiative involves the adoption of regular expressions (regex) for defining PID types. Additionally, as part of this standardisation effort, PID types will be equipped with their own identifiers (PIDs), facilitating their unique identification and management. By incorporating regex patterns into the type definition, PID types become easily accessible and universally applicable across various contexts. This approach ensures that PID types are consistently defined and readily usable within the system.

3.4.2 Expected Benefits

PID Metaresolver plays a crucial role in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, enabling the resolution of Persistent Identifiers and providing access to rich metadata associated with research outputs. By promoting interoperability, scalability, and compliance with FAIR principles, the PIDMR facilitates the discovery, access, and reuse of research resources, ultimately advancing the objectives of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project and

benefiting the research community as a whole. PIDMR helps to harmonise the resolvability of the PIDs by hiding the complexity and keeping the knowledge on where to route different types of identifiers internally. In order to support that PID Metaresolver provides standardised interfaces for users and programmatic use. These interfaces allow easy use regardless of technical details, ensuring easy access to resources. For providers of PID systems, or more precisely, of resolvers for PIDs, PIDMR provides its own interface for supporting the different PIDs systems/frameworks. This means that the scope of resources can be continuously expanded. PIDMR can therefore also be integrated into research information systems in which a large number of different PID types are used to enrich the research information system with additional metadata.

3.5 EOSC Metadata and Schema Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)

3.5.1 Introduction

The MSCR allows registered users and communities to create, register and version metadata schemas and crosswalks with PIDs. The published content can be searched, browsed and downloaded without restrictions. The MSCR also provides an API to facilitate the transformation of data from one schema to another via registered crosswalks. This is a type of component that will not integrate much with other components, but other components will integrate with the MSCR, in order to use the main functionalities.

Integrations that benefit from Metadata and Schema Crosswalk Registry functionality:

MSCR functions as a component for integration, enabling other components to seamlessly integrate with it. The MSCR supports other components with the possibility to manage their metadata schema and/or relevant metadata schema crosswalks. The components that are going to use the functionalities of MSCR are described below. The functionalities that are going to be used are described in the corresponding components paragraph.

- **Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph):** This is already described in the **RDGraph paragraph**.
- **PID Graph (PIDGraph):** This is already described in the **PIDGraph paragraph**.
- **PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR):** This integration is already described in the **PIDMR paragraph**.

Apart from the FAIRCORE4EOSC components, current available features in MSCR GUI and API have been developed to meet requirements of the case studies and demonstrator and MSCR Components team has been in touch with them to facilitate the integration through handover workshops, feedback sheets and support emails. The functionalities are described in the Case Studies Section.

3.5.1.1 Vocabulary Service

Vocabulary mappings are an important part of the operationalization of mappings created with the MSCR. When allowed values of a schema element associated with a mapping are restricted to specific vocabulary values, it is necessary to perform a value mapping as part of the data transformation or crosswalk process. In order to do this, another mapping between vocabularies is required.

A vocabulary service component was added to the list of developed components to support the MSCR as well as other work packages that require a tool for managing different kinds of vocabularies. The vocabulary service is based on the Finnish Interoperability Platform's Terminology tool, with customizations related to the PIDs for vocabularies and concepts as well as SKOS related import and export functionality.

The Vocabulary Service is a tool for creating and maintaining vocabularies. The vocabularies are structured according to the SKOS-XL model, which creates separate resources for vocabulary, concepts and terms. New concepts can be inputted manually or imported using XML, Excel or SKOS RDF format. The content can be versioned and status of the vocabulary, concept and term can be defined independently. Users can subscribe

to receive email notifications about changes to the selected vocabularies. The service supports multilingual UI and content (concept labels).

3.5.2 Expected Benefits

The Metadata schema and cross-walk registry (MSCR) is the component that is currently supporting most of the components to manage their metadata schema and/or relevant metadata schema crosswalks. By defining common data models and formats, MSCR ensures consistency in metadata representation across different components and services, facilitating interoperability and data exchange. By providing this flexible, interoperable, and community-driven approach to metadata management, MSCR serves as a foundational component for metadata management within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. MSCR offers a range of benefits that support efficient, standardized, and collaborative approaches to metadata organization and discovery such as

- A harmonized and public view to the schemas and crosswalks.
- Explicit and available target and source schemas associated with the crosswalk allowing the validation of both input and output data.
- Changes to schemas and crosswalks are controlled (versioning) and visible to all
- Users can be notified of crosswalk's source and target schema changes and assess whether a new version of the crosswalk is needed as well.
- Crosswalks can be edited and commented by multiple parties (e.g. owners of the source and target schema)
- Crosswalks can be expressed in different machine-readable formats (i.e. SSSOM) that are designed for operationalization (instead of e.g. PDF or custom CSV/Excel files).

3.6 EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)

3.6.1 Introduction

The EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR) allows the registration of many different FAIR data types. The goal is to achieve a high degree in machine actionability and interoperability in the management of structured research data. Each data type is assigned a persistent identifier for unambiguous identification, along with a set of provenance information and type specific fields. The main integrations that have already been achieved or are under consideration are as follows:

The [PID Metaresolver](#) is already described in the **PID Metaresolver paragraph**

DTR - PID Meta Resolver

The cross-integration of the Data Type Registry with the PID Meta Resolver is given by the nature of the types registered in the DTR. Since each type is automatically assigned a Handle persistent identifier, each type is consequentially resolvable via the PIDMR.

DTR - MSCR

The Data Type Registry and MSCR welcome a lot of integration from their respective fields of application, especially from the DTR to the MSCR. Many types produced by the DTR can, in some way or another, be used in the MSCR. A complete schema that is defined in the DTR can be registered as a metadata schema in the MSCR and thus be made available for crosswalks. Thus, it was crucial to establish an interface that allows the exchange of data between the services. Also, single datatypes of the DTR can be set as properties in existing schemas in the MSCR via persistent identifiers. The DTR exposes an interface that allows the MSCR to exploit the nuanced faceting system to enable users of the MSCR to find appropriate data types for their respective requirements.

DTR - Vocabulary Service

The vocabulary service as mentioned in the MSCR component introduced during the FAIRCORE4EOSC project allows the registration of controlled vocabularies. Controlled lists of values can also be used in the DTR to set a list of allowed values for a field. The vocabulary service offers an endpoint that returns a registered vocabulary in the required format to be directly included in a registered type. This allows users to shift the management of controlled lists of values to another service.

3.6.2 Expected Benefits

The Data Type Registry (DTR) promotes standardisation, improves data quality, and supports the overall objectives of the project in advancing open and transparent research data management practices. The DTR enhances standardisation by providing a centralised repository for defining, documenting and validating data types. This ensures consistency and coherence in data representation across different components and services within the FAIRCORE4EOSC ecosystem. At the same time, the representation of metadata as crosswalks via the **MSCR** enhances data discovery. The cross-integration of the **DTR** with the Vocabulary Service leads to interoperability by allowing the use of registered vocabularies as controlled lists of values in the DTR.

The next steps regarding the cross integration of other components with the DTR are the actual operationalization of the integration beyond proofs of concept. We expect to show the added value of the DTR to the larger ecosystem of interconnected components that are actually in production mode.

3.7 EOSC Research Activity Identifier (RAiD)

3.7.1 Introduction

RAiD provides a globally unique persistent identifier and a metadata record for research projects and activities (broadly defined), connecting research projects to people, organisations, inputs, and outputs. A demonstration environment of EOSC RAiD, newly incorporating DOIs as the identifier for RAiD, is available to project participants and EOSC demonstrator projects. This environment includes a web application (offering a GUI for interacting with RAiD) and an API, supporting integration into existing research management systems.

3.7.2 Expected Benefits

The EOSC RAiD service supports administration of project information:

- Reliable information management: Record research project or activity information under one unique RAiD name for easy discovery, updating and sharing with others
- Seamless backend integration and interoperability: Combine all your research information into one accessible and standardised RAiD metadata record from any device.
- project reporting: The RAiD can be submitted to stakeholders in support of planned project reporting events, together with narrative accounts of project status.
- Strategic monitoring: RAiD enables tracking of project inputs and outputs to gain strategic insight into project outcomes or impact at any time.

FC4E cross component benefits:

- The recent strategic partnership between ARDC and DataCite⁶ simplifies ingestion of RAiD into the PID Graph. As the persistent identifier for RAiDs will be minted as DOIs via DataCite, ingestion RAiD project information into the PIDgraph requires minimal development from either party.
- Availability of RAiD project information in the DataCite PID Graph thereby enables easy access for other research graph systems. The RDgraph will ingest RAiDs via DataCite PID Graph.

The RAiD demonstration environment⁷ for testing, demonstrating, or experimenting includes the following:

- A web application (offering a GUI for interacting with RAiD) and an API, supporting integration into existing research management systems
- At present, a subset of RAiD metadata, sufficient to build the PID Graph, will be submitted to DataCite and incorporated into the graph
- Authentication facilitated by Keycloak, offering AAI and EDUgain as options (among others)

3.8 Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC)

In the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, WP6 is dedicated to developing tools and services crucial for archiving, referencing, describing, and citing research software artefacts.

The RSAC (Research Software APIs and Connectors) component is organized into six sub-components, each dedicated to specific infrastructures within scholarly repositories, publishers, and aggregators. All subcomponents released a minimal viable product in the Beta release in November 2023 which was a significant milestone in the FAIRCORE4EOSC journey and in achieving the SIRS reports recommendations. The MS33 milestone, submitted by CERN under Work Package 6 (WP6), Services and tools to archive, reference, describe and cite research software, as a short report summarizing the BETA cross-integration software report for Research Software APIs and Connectors (RSAC) sub-components.

3.8.1 Subcomponents status report

The focus after the BETA-RELEASE has been to prepare for and collect user feedback. This has involved the preparation of end-user documentation and demonstration videos, and a cross-subcomponent test plan for conducting the initial user testing and providing feedback. The test plan reviews if the RSAC subcomponents are compliant with the SIRS report's foreseen user interactions as detailed in the technical user specifications. The primary goal is to establish a cohesive interconnection among scholarly repositories, publishers, and aggregators. The interoperability between the sub-components of the RSAC (Research Software APIs and Connectors) and other components within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project is crucial for enabling seamless metadata exchange and utilization of the RSAC API endpoints. To achieve this interoperability, the following strategies are employed:

- **Use of CodeMeta Vocabulary:** The use of the CodeMeta vocabulary provides a standardised framework for describing research software metadata. This ensures consistency and coherence in metadata representation across different components and services within the FAIRCORE4EOSC ecosystem.
- **Mappings:** Mappings are developed between different vocabularies and the CodeMeta standard also used in the **MSCR** component. This facilitates the alignment of metadata descriptions from various

⁶ ARDC and DataCite Announce Partnership to Deliver the RAiD Service <https://ardc.edu.au/article/ardc-and-datacite-announce-partnership-to-deliver-the-raid-service>

⁷ Request access or log into the RAiD demonstrator here: <https://app.demo.raid.org.au/login>

sources with the CodeMeta schema , enabling interoperability and data exchange between different systems and platforms.

- **Referencing with SWHID:** Code artefacts are referenced using Software Hash Identifiers (SWHID⁸). SWHIDs provide unique and persistent identifiers for software artefacts, ensuring their traceability and citability.
- Cross-integration with the other FAIRCORE4EOSC components happen primarily through use of standardised metadata (Codemeta) also used in the **MSCR** component.

By leveraging these strategies, the integration of the RSAC sub-components with other FAIRCORE4EOSC components is streamlined and standardised. This ensures that metadata exchange processes are efficient and effective, promoting interoperability and collaboration within the project ecosystem.

Following is an overview of the cross-integration status for each subcomponent with links to documentation, test system, and a video demonstration of the integration:

T6.1 Scholarly repositories - InvenioRDM (CERN)⁹

In terms of cross-integration^{10,11}InvenioRDM crosswalks its internal metadata model into DataCite v4.3 schema, Codemeta (JSON-LD), Dublin Core, MARCXML, BibTeX, DCAT and CFF. The Codemeta (JSON-LD) is embedded in landing pages for search engines, the DataCite metadata is registered via DOIs which makes it available in the RDGraph, and the Codemeta is submitted to the universal source code archive (SWH). The SWHID is integrated into metadata to link SWHID and the DOI. Submissions are in addition sent to the OpenAIRE Graph.

T6.1 Scholarly repositories - DANS - SWH APIs and connectors (DANS)¹²

This task has detailed information on how a researcher can start depositing software code and associated datasets to a dataset repository (Dataverse instance) and to the Software Heritage (SWH) archive. The DANS-deposit¹³ form uses a mapping service that maps the form-data to f.i. SWH SWORD2 fields. Detailed information can be found from here <https://dans-labs.github.io/swh-docs/>

T6.2 Publishers - Dagstuhl - SWH APIs and connectors (LZI)¹⁴

In terms of cross-integration, Dagstuhl uses codemeta representation for SW associated with publications and worked on its conversion to three main formats: BibTex, BibLatex, and Datacite. Publishing such metadata is in due process on our infrastructure. During papers' submission process, we are also working on retrieving some available metadata from repositories (e.g. github, citation.cff) and have them converted to Codemeta before eventually asking authors to enrich that codemeta using a user-friendly interface. Detailed documentation can be found at the repository¹⁵, at github¹⁶.

⁸ <https://www.swhid.org/specification/v1.1/>

⁹ Scholarly repositories - InvenioRDM (CERN) Test instance - <https://sandbox.zenodo.org>

¹⁰ Documentation: <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/deposit/create-new-upload/>

¹¹ Video demo: <https://cernbox.cern.ch/s/IWS6qnEN5yB2S0S>

¹² Test system: <https://swh.dansdemo.nl/>

¹³The service code is located here: <https://github.com/Dans-labs/dans-xslt/blob/main/faircore4eosc/faircore4eosc-form-metadata-to-swd-sword-v1.xsl>

¹⁴ Test system: <https://faircore4eosc.dagstuhl.de/>

¹⁵ Documentation: <https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/codemeta-crosswalk>

¹⁶Documentation: <https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-client/blob/main/README.md>

T6.2 Publishers - Episciences - SWH APIs and connectors (INRIA)¹⁷

In terms of cross-integration, Episcience prose Notify protocol (<https://www.coar-repositories.org/notify/>) with information about link with software and/or data. Next step is working on including software information in the different export format from episcience. Detailed documentation can be found from here¹⁸.

T6.3 Aggregators - SwMATH - SWH APIs and connectors (FIZ)¹⁹

SwMATH is currently processing software metadata to be ingested in the PID Graph since an OAI-PMH server of the MaRDI infrastructure. The same OAI-PMH server will help with exposing metadata in the RSAC-swMATH subcomponent instance. Detailed documentation can be found from here²⁰.

T6.3 Aggregators - OpenAIRE - SWH APIs and connectors (OPENAIRE)

The OpenAIRE - SWH connector component integrates with the RDGraph component developed in WP3. In particular, during the RDGraph provision workflow, SWH ids are collected from SWH for all software entities in the graph. These are then made available through the RDGraph portals (<https://beta.rdgraph.openaire.eu/>) as well as the relevant graph APIs. Meanwhile, software code repositories present in the RDGraph but not indexed in SWH, are submitted to the SWH APIs in order to be saved/indexed.

3.8.2 Cross-Integration next steps

The RSAC sub-components are at the BETA testing phase which will result with the analysis and review of the current available functionalities and the level of integration with other sub-components within WP6 and with other FAIRCORE4EOSC components. Following the first internal review and within the iterative development process, the sub-components leads will identify adequate adjustments and improvements.

The next BETA release will undergo a community review with external users. In addition to the external review, the case studies that are using the RSAC sub-component will present the possible workflows where multiple components are integrated. The mathematics case study will seamlessly showcase how mathematical software metadata are dispatched along a workflow feeding the RSAC, the PIDGraph and the RDGraph as well.

Finally, the PROD release at the end of the project will include the interoperability functionalities that were identified as appropriate for the sub-components and aligned with the most suited integration with other components.

3.8.3 Expected Benefits

The interoperability between the sub-components and with the other FAIRCORE4EOSC components is essential for ensuring metadata exchange and usage of the provided RSAC API endpoints. This is accomplished through integration with the **Software Heritage universal source code archive**, using the **CodeMeta standard**, and **incorporating Software Hash identifiers (SWHID)**. By leveraging these strategies, the integration of the RSAC sub-components with other FAIRCORE4EOSC components is streamlined and standardised. This ensures that metadata exchange processes are efficient and effective,

¹⁷ Test service: <https://epijinfo.episciences.org/>

¹⁸ Documentation <https://doc.episciences.org/software/>

¹⁹ Test service https://staging.swmath.org/wiki/Main_Page?swid=1003

²⁰Documentation:

https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/swMATH4EOSC/blob/main/user_documentation/documentation_for_swMATH_users.md

promoting interoperability and collaboration within the project ecosystem. Ultimately, these efforts contribute to the overall FAIRness and usability of research software artefacts within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

4 EOSC Core Components integration

4.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the current status of integration of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Components with the existing EOSC Core components such as they were operated by the EOSC Future Project (AAI, Accounting, Monitoring Messaging, Resource Catalogue, Providers Portal, Catalogue & Marketplace).

In order to foster and support further the integration of FAIRCORE4EOSC components with EOSC Core, a series of dedicated workshops were scheduled for April 2024. These workshops aimed to familiarise developers of each component with each EOSC Core component and the corresponding interoperability guidelines to make use of them.

The topics of these workshops were:

- Connecting to the EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy, or joining the EOSC AAI Federation/eduGAIN
- Have your serviced through the EOSC Monitoring service
- How to publish service and research product accounting figures in EOSC
- Integrate with the EOSC Helpdesk
- Make your research products discoverable in EOSC
- Onboard your service into the EOSC Exchange

In this chapter we also highlight the lessons learned through this process and identify possible gaps to be fed into SRIA 2.0 if possible.

4.2 Current Status

At the time of writing the following components have already been integrated with EOSC Core components, the rest are planned to follow in the next period (demo instances).

In the table below you may see the integrations of FAIRCORE4EOSC components with the EOSC Core components. The “ready” tag defines that the FAIRCORE4EOSC components have already been integrated with EOSC Core components, or that they have followed the guidelines and are ready to be integrated. The “planning” tag defines the FAIRCORE4EOSC components that are planning to integrate with the EOSC Core Components.

Table 4 – Status of integrations of FAIRCORE4EOSC components with the EOSC Core components.

	EOSC AAI	EOSC Helpdesk	EOSC Monitoring	EOSC Accounting for Services	EOSC Exchange
CAT	ready	planning	ready	not	planning
RD Graph	planning				investigating
PID Graph	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	planning
MSCR	ready	planning	planning	planning	planning
DTR	planning				planning
PIDMR	ready	planning	ready	investigating	planning
RAiD	ready				planning
RSAC					planning

4.2.1 EOSC Metadata and Schema Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)

MSCR is integrated with the demo EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure proxy to authenticate its users in the beta release platform <https://mscr-test.rahtiapp.fi>. Users can log in with different credentials supported by EOSC AAI and create and browse content in MSCR. MSCR has also plans to integrate with the EOSC Monitoring and Accounting Service and Helpdesk later in the project timeline.

4.2.2 EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)

The Data Type Registry will be connected to the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure proxy to allow users to authenticate themselves with their institute credentials in an easy and federated way. The integration is still in the planning stage.

4.2.3 EOSC Research Activity Identifier (RAID)

The present EOSC Marketplace (MP) integration strategy is to establish the EOSC RAiD service via the RAiD Service software operated by SURF, with an API token allowing MP users to create, retrieve, and edit RAiDs. Users will only have to create an independent account with RAiD if they wish to use the native RAiD web application to update their RAiDS.

4.2.4 EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit - CAT

The CAT is following all the interoperability guidelines required to integrate with the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure proxy. Currently, it is integrated with the demo instance of the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure proxy to test its functionality for both Authentication and Authorisation.

To ensure the security of all interactions, the CAT API is protected via tokens by the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure proxy, safeguarding each endpoint. Clients can obtain specific roles that determine their access permissions, defining which endpoints they can interact with. The CAT API also empowers administrators with efficient and dynamic user management capabilities, allowing them to control the validation process and roles. At the same time, CAT-UI supports different levels of authorization for registered users, separating the UI capabilities for administrators and simple users.

From the **EOSC Monitoring perspective**, CAT has created an api health-check endpoint based on the interoperability guidelines. There is a broad range of items that this API health check endpoint can check. It mainly checks anything (ex. database connection) that may interrupt the API from serving incoming requests.

4.2.5 EOSC PID Metaresolver - PIDMR

The PIDMR also follows all the interoperability guidelines required to integrate with the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure proxy. Currently, it is integrated with the demo instance of the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure proxy to test its functionality for both Authentication and Authorisation.

PID Metaresolver is also protected via tokens by the EOSC AAI Core Infrastructure proxy, safeguarding each endpoint. Providers can login to the service and obtain the provider role in order to add the required information about the PID they provide. At the same time administrators can accept or reject the new provider request. API also empowers administrators with efficient and dynamic user management capabilities, allowing them to control the validation process and roles.

information while administrators manage user roles and validation processes via API. This setup enhances security and ensures efficient management of PID-related operations.

From the **EOSC Monitoring perspective**, PIDMR has created an API health-check²¹ endpoint based on the interoperability guidelines. It is a Rest(ful) API endpoint that checks the API itself and all critical dependencies. API health check endpoint returns the check result as the response. This endpoint can be used by the EOSC Monitoring service to check the availability and the status of the PIDMR-API.

4.3 Next Steps

As communicated by the EC, the EOSC Providers Portal and the EOSC Catalogue & Marketplace will be phased out as of 15 April 2024. The rest of the Services are expected to be phased out soon after that deadline as they will be replaced by their equivalents operated by the EOSC EU Node operators. The EOSC EU Node operators will ensure the discoverability and findability (search functions) of existing services from mid-April. Full features of the EOSC EU Node are expected to go live in the second half of 2024.

The EOSC EU node however will be governed by different policies and procedures, which are not available at this point and it is expected to be focused on delivering production-managed services rather than acting as an incubator/sandbox. The evolution of the current EOSC Core component and their adaptation to become compatible with the new EOSC Federation model is expected to be continued by the EOSC Beyond Project²². The EOSC Beyond project is expected to offer the EOSC Core innovation sandbox which will offer the possibility to pilot integrations with the state-of-the-art EOSC Core components and services. FAIRCORE4EOSC will therefore focus its integration with the core platform by making use of the EOSC Core innovation sandbox when it becomes available as this will help to expedite the process. The EOSC Association is in the process of establishing the opportunity areas for a number of subjects including EOSC Core and FAIRCORE4EOSC is one of the projects invited to contribute with its feedback on how the EOSC Architecture can be improved and extended in the future.

²¹ <https://api.pidmr.argo.grnet.gr/v1/healthcheck>

²² <https://eosc.eu/eu-project/eosc-beyond/>

5 References

No	Description/Link
R1	https://zenodo.org/records/10518813
R2	https://zenodo.org/records/10518813
R3	https://zenodo.org/records/10518813
R4	Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework (SKIG-IF: https://skg-if.readthedocs.io/en/latest/)
R5	CERIF Common European Research Information Format
R6	ARDC and DataCite Announce Partnership to Deliver the RAiD Service https://ardc.edu.au/article/ardc-and-datacite-announce-partnership-to-deliver-the-raid-service
R7	Request access or log into the RAiD demonstrator here: https://app.demo.raid.org.au/login
R8	https://www.swhid.org/specification/v1.1/
R9	Scholarly repositories - InvenioRDM (CERN) Test instance - https://sandbox.zenodo.org
R10	Documentation: https://help.zenodo.org/docs/deposit/create-new-upload/
R11	Video demo: https://cernbox.cern.ch/s/IWS6qnEN5yB2S0S
R12	Test system: https://sw.h.dansdemo.nl/
R13	The service code is located here: https://github.com/Dans-labs/dans-xslt/blob/main/faircore4eosc/faircore4eosc-form-metadata-to-swd-sword-v1.xsl
R14	Test system: https://faircore4eosc.dagstuhl.de/
R15	Documentation: https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/codemeta-crosswalk
R16	Documentation: https://github.com/dagstuhl-publishing/swh-client/blob/main/README.md
R17	Test service: https://epijinfo.episciences.org/
R18	Documentation https://doc.episciences.org/software/
R19	Test service https://staging.swmath.org/wiki/Main_Page?swid=1003
R20	Documentation: https://github.com/MaRDI4NFDI/swMATH4EOSC/blob/main/user_documentation/documentation_for_swMATH_users.md
R21	https://api.pidmr.argo.grnet.gr/v1/healthcheck
R22	https://eosc.eu/eu-project/eosc-beyond/